

Beyond The Classroom: Narratives Of Junior High School Teachers On Self-Regulated Learning Strategies

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Abstract. This study aimed to explore the experiences of Junior High School Teachers on Self-Regulated Learning Strategies through qualitative phenomenology, utilizing a narrative inquiry approach from ten (10) participants. The findings revealed that the junior high school teachers' diverse experiences offer a compelling glimpse into their personal experiences, fostering innovation and teaching students to manage their time efficiently. The emerging themes of challenges and coping mechanisms involved in implementing self-regulated learning strategies are significant, as teachers often encounter obstacles when applying self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies. These challenges include difficulties in adapting and being flexible in their teaching methods, ensuring active student participation, and facilitating meaningful discussions. The insights regarding the impact and effectiveness of self-regulated learning strategies in enhancing academic success among students, such as the success of self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies in improving educational achievement, are significantly influenced by three main factors: high teacher motivation, intensified institutional support, and strengthened parent and teacher collaboration. Motivated teachers are essential, as they inspire students, model effective self-regulated learning (SRL) techniques, and create a classroom environment conducive to autonomous learning. They may also explore different challenges and strategies to open new avenues to improve learners' learning. They may also publish in reputable journals to ensure that work is accessible and can serve as a foundation for future research.

KEY WORDS 1. Narratives 2. Self-Regulated Learning 3. Junior High School Teachers' Strategies

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1. Introduction

Self-regulated learning (SRL) has long been recognized as essential for student success, emphasizing goal-setting, self-monitoring, and reflective practices. However, much of the existing research centers on students, often overlooking how teachers engage in self-regulated learning. This creates a noticeable gap between theory and practice, where teachers are expected to cultivate Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) in their classrooms without fully understanding or experiencing its application in their professional lives. Exploring this gap offers valuable insights into how teachers manage their learning, adapt to challenges, and develop strategies that support their growth and that of their students. Challenges have been observed in effectively integrating self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies in classroom settings. In Turkey, middle school students' self-regulation skills and vocabulary learning strategies varied significantly by gen-

der and grade level, indicating inconsistencies in SRL application (Gorgoz Tican, 2020). In Nigeria, self-regulated learning skills have a positive influence on mathematics achievement among secondary school students. However, notable gender differences emerged, with male students gaining greater academic benefits from these strategies compared to their female peers (Duru et al., 2023). This highlights the importance of targeted interventions to strengthen self-regulated learning (SRL) among female learners. In Malaysia during the pandemic (Anthonyamy et al., 2021), various barriers hindered the effective use of SRL in online learning environments. These included technical issues and low student motivation, both of which disrupted the consistent application of SRL strategies. In the Philippines, the shift to online learning brought significant challenges for both students and teachers. Limited access to technology and ineffective online instructional methods negatively impacted the use of SRL strategies in secondary education (Maranan, 2021). Findings from work on science education suggest that while teacher competency contributes to student learning, the structure of the online laboratory environment plays a more significant role in supporting Self-Regulated Learning (SRL), particularly in science-related subjects (Zabala Dayaganon, 2022). In preparation for mathematics exams, high-achieving students demonstrated the use of more effective self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies than their lower-achieving counterparts. This suggests a need for additional support to help all learners develop and apply these skills (Türker Biber, 2022). In Davao City, educators reported difficulties in promoting self-regulated learn-

ing (SRL) among junior high school students. Many faced challenges in adjusting teaching methods to support independent learning in both face-to-face and online settings. While classroom strategies were widely implemented in Davao del Norte, a deeper local understanding is still needed to better align instructional practices with SRL goals (Perez, 2024). Despite these efforts, limited attention has been given to the voices of junior high school teachers in the Philippine context, particularly in Davao City. Exploring their experiences and perspectives is crucial to developing effective, context-sensitive SRL approaches. Addressing this gap can lead to more responsive teaching strategies, improved student outcomes, and a stronger foundation for fostering self-regulated learning.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to explore the personal experiences and insights of junior high school teachers in District 2, Division of Davao City, regarding the role of self-regulated learning strategies in promoting academic success among their students. Using a narrative qualitative approach, the research aimed to understand how teachers perceived, implemented, and reflected upon self-regulated learning strategies in the classroom. It sought to uncover the strategies teachers used to foster self-regulation in students, the challenges they encountered, and the impact of these strategies on students' academic achievement, providing valuable insights into how self-regulation could be integrated into teaching practices for enhanced learning outcomes.

1.2. Research Questions —The main research questions guiding this study are as follows:

- (1) What personal experiences do junior high school teachers in District II, Cluster IV, have in applying self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms?
- (2) What challenges do junior high school teachers face in implementing self-regulated learning strategies, and what coping mechanisms or strategies do they use to overcome these obstacles?

- (3) What insights do junior high school teachers have regarding the impact and effectiveness of self-regulated learning strategies in enhancing student academic success?

This study holds great potential for various beneficiaries, including the following:

1.2.1. Junior High School Teachers—This study held significant value for various stakeholders in the education system, starting with junior high school teachers. By exploring their experiences and insights into self-regulated learning strategies, the study gave teachers a deeper understanding of how these strategies could enhance student motivation, engagement, and academic success. The findings offered practical recommendations that could be integrated into their teaching methods, allowing them to better support students in developing essential self-regulation skills that contribute to academic achievement.

1.2.2. Students—For students, the ultimate beneficiaries of this study, the research emphasized the importance of self-regulation in academic success. By highlighting the role of teachers in guiding students to adopt these strategies, the study indirectly enhanced student learning outcomes by encouraging more tailored and effective teaching practices.

1.3. Review of Significant Literature—Self-Regulated Learning (SRL): Concept and Importance Self-regulated learning (SRL) emphasizes students' ability to control their learning through goal-setting, self-monitoring, and reflection (Panadero, 2022). Recognized globally for promoting autonomy, adaptability, and academic success, SRL aligns with 21st-century educational priorities such as critical thinking and lifelong learning. Teachers play a vital role in modeling and fostering SRL, particularly in diverse junior high school classrooms.

1.3.1. Theoretical Foundations—SRL is grounded in Zimmerman's (2022) cyclical model involving forethought, performance, and self-reflection. Vygotsky's sociocultural theory and Bandura's social cognitive theory fur-

ther highlight the influence of social interaction and self-efficacy in developing SRL (Boekaerts Corno, 2021; Schunk DiBenedetto, 2020). Teachers enhance SRL by creating supportive, scaffolded learning environments. Technological tools like AI-powered planners and adaptive platforms also support SRL through personalized learning and feedback (Somasundaram et al., 2020; Carter et al., 2023).

1.3.2. Global Perspectives—Worldwide, SRL strategies are embedded in various educational systems. In Europe and Asia, teacher training and curriculum design have emphasized SRL integration (Hadwin et al., 2020; Yamada Fujita, 2020). North America has applied SRL in digital and blended learning environments, enhancing student performance and independence (Carter et al., 2023; Schunk DiBenedetto, 2020). In developing regions like Africa and South America, SRL is promoted to bridge educational inequities (OECD, 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic further underscored SRL's value in supporting remote and autonomous learning (Panadero, 2022).

1.3.3. National Perspective: The Philippine Context—The Philippines has incorporated SRL into the K to 12 curriculum, aligning with goals of fostering critical thinking and learner independence (DepEd, 2020). SRL is especially valuable in addressing disparities caused by socioeconomic and geographic challenges (Garcia et al., 2021). During the pandemic, SRL became essential for students navigating modular and online learning environments, especially when supported by home environments and digital access (Santos et al., 2021).

Educators have been pivotal in integrating SRL. Initiatives by institutions like Philippine Normal University focus on training teachers in SRL strategies (Bernardo et al., 2022). Programs like the Alternative Learning System

(ALS) also incorporate SRL principles to serve out-of-school youth and adult learners (DepEd, 2023).

1.3.4. Challenges and Opportunities—Key barriers to SRL implementation include limited access to digital tools, inadequate teacher training, and reliance on traditional teaching methods (Cabual et al., 2021; De Guzman Santiago, 2023). However, opportunities emerge through DepEd’s learner-centered initiatives such as Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions, hybrid learning modalities, and increased emphasis on mental health and well-being. These developments support the integration of SRL and foster holistic student growth (Santos Reyes, 2022; Manalo et al., 2020; Lopez Carreon, 2024).

1.4. Synthesis—The reviewed literature underscored the growing importance of self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies as a pivotal framework for fostering student autonomy, motivation, and academic success. Globally, SRL was widely recognized as a transformative tool that equipped students to set goals, manage time, and reflect on their learning processes. Theoretical models such as Zimmerman’s (2022) Cyclical Phases of Self-Regulation provided a robust foundation for understanding the interplay between SRL’s cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational aspects. Recent studies affirmed that SRL promoted lifelong learning skills, particularly in environments encouraging reflective practices and autonomy. In the Philippine context, the application of SRL strategies presented a blend of challenges and opportunities. Resource constraints, traditional teaching practices, and insufficient teacher training were persistent barriers to the widespread adoption of SRL frameworks. However, the Department of Education (DepEd) initiatives and the gradual shift toward hybrid learning environments signaled a positive trajectory. Emerging programs and policies emphasized aligning SRL strategies with learner-centered pedagogies, creat-

ing potential pathways for integrating SRL into mainstream education. These developments highlighted the critical role of teachers in fostering an environment conducive to self-regulation. Locally, in Davao City, educators faced unique challenges in implementing SRL strategies due to contextual factors such as varying access to resources, class sizes, and cultural expectations. Despite these obstacles, some teachers demonstrated innovative approaches to cultivating self-regulation among students, leveraging available resources and tailoring strategies to suit learners’ needs. This localized lens revealed a complex interplay between systemic challenges and individual agency, highlighting the importance of context-specific solutions to SRL implementation. The literature synthesis revealed a research gap in exploring the lived experiences of junior high school teachers in applying self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies within their classrooms. While global and national studies provided valuable insights, there was a lack of empirical evidence focusing on Filipino educators’ narratives and personal perspectives, particularly in urban settings such as Davao City. Addressing this gap could enrich the understanding of how teachers navigated challenges, adapted strategies, and perceived the impact of SRL on student outcomes. This study, therefore, aimed to bridge this gap by shedding light on the nuanced experiences of junior high school teachers and their efforts to integrate SRL into their teaching practices.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This research was grounded in Zimmerman’s Self-Regulated Learning Theory (2022), Vygotsky’s Sociocultural Theory (McLeod, 2025), and Bandura’s Social Cognitive Theory (Nickerson, 2025) to investigate the self-regulated learning strategies utilized by junior high school teachers in District 2, Cluster 14 of the Davao City Division. These theoretical models were crucial for understanding how educators assist students in actively engaging with their learning

by implementing self-regulated learning techniques. Combining these perspectives offered a well-rounded approach to examining the cognitive, social, and motivational elements that affect how self-regulated learning is practiced in the classroom. Additionally, these frameworks helped guide the study of the various challenges and achievements teachers experienced while promoting their students' academic development. Zimmerman's Self-Regulated Learning Theory (2022) provided a foundational framework for understanding how junior high school teachers in District 2, Division of Davao City, implemented self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms. Zimmerman's theory posited that self-regulated learning involved three key phases: forethought, performance, and self-reflection. Teachers were instrumental in guiding students through these phases by helping them set learning goals, monitor their progress, and evaluate their learning strategies. By contextualizing this theory within teachers' experiences, the study aimed to explore how educators facilitated self-regulation in students, the strategies they used to help students manage their learning, and how these strategies influenced academic success. This theory allowed the study to examine the practical application of self-regulated learning from a teacher's perspective and its impact on students' motivation and performance. Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (McLeod, 2025) offered an additional layer of context to the study by emphasizing the importance of social interactions and cultural tools in the learning process. According to Vygotsky, students developed cognitive and metacognitive skills through collaborative learning, guided by more knowledgeable others (teachers or peers). In self-regulated learning, teachers scaffolded students' learning by providing the support needed to help them develop self-regulation skills within their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). By integrating Vygotsky's theory, the study explored how teachers used interactive teaching methods, feedback, and peer collaboration to support students in mastering self-regulated learning strategies. This theory emphasized the collaborative nature of learning and the crucial role of teachers in fostering environments where students could gradually develop self-regulation skills. Finally, Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (Nickerson, 2025) emphasized the role of self-efficacy in learning, suggesting that students' belief in their ability to succeed played a critical role in their motivation and engagement. By modeling self-regulated learning behaviors such as goal setting, time management, and self-monitoring, teachers influenced students' self-efficacy, thus enhancing their ability to self-regulate their learning. This theory was particularly useful in understanding the reciprocal relationship between teachers' behaviors and students' learning outcomes. By contextualizing Bandura's theory within the study, the research examined how teachers' self-regulated learning strategies and their self-efficacy impacted students' academic success. The study also explored how teachers' modeling of these strategies fostered an environment where students could develop the confidence and skills needed to regulate their learning, ultimately contributing to improved academic outcomes. This study's conceptual framework focused on the intertwined elements of Personal Experiences, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms, and Insights on Effectiveness, which together aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how junior high school teachers in Davao City applied self-regulated learning strategies. The first component, Personal Experiences, delved into how teachers implemented self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms, considering the various factors influencing their teaching methods. These experiences formed the foundation for understanding teachers' strategies, the difficulties they faced, and how their teaching philosophies shaped their approach to foster

ing student independence. Teachers' narratives were essential in contextualizing their strategies, allowing for a nuanced exploration of the day-to-day realities they navigated. The second component, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms, explored teachers' obstacles in effectively applying self-regulated learning strategies. These challenges included large class sizes, diverse student needs, limited resources, and a lack of student motivation. The framework emphasized how teachers addressed these challenges through various coping mechanisms such as differentiated instruction, personalized feedback, and fostering a classroom environment that encouraged self-reflection and accountability. By understanding these coping strategies, the study provided insights into how teachers adapted their teaching practices to maintain an effective learning environment and ensured that students could develop self-regulation skills despite these barriers. The third component, Insights on Effectiveness, brought together teachers' reflections on the success and limitations of self-regulated learning strategies in promoting academic achievement. Teachers' perceptions of how these strategies impacted student motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes were crucial in evaluating the overall effectiveness of self-regulation in the classroom. By examining the intersection of these three components, the conceptual framework offered a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at work in junior high school classrooms. The interconnections between teachers' experiences, the challenges they overcame, and their insights into effectiveness yielded valuable in-

sights into how self-regulated learning strategies could be optimized to improve academic success and foster student independence in learning. Self-regulated learning (SRL) enables students to achieve strong academic results and meet their learning goals online. Despite this, many learners struggle to implement SRL strategies in virtual environments effectively. Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) applications have shown the potential to support and enhance students' self-regulation during online learning by assessing and promoting SRL. However, research on this topic remains in its early stages. (Jin et al., 2023). Shown in Figure 1 was the interconnection between the two research questions: the Lived Personal Experiences of Junior High School Teachers in Applying Self-Regulated Learning Strategies, and the Coping Mechanisms for the challenges encountered by secondary school teachers from Personal Experiences of Junior High School Teachers in Applying Self-Regulated Learning Strategies, which resulted in the common denominator, Insights Learned from the experiences of junior secondary school teachers. This interconnection illustrates how teachers' firsthand experiences with implementing SRL directly shape the coping strategies they develop in response to classroom challenges. Through a dynamic process of trial, reflection, and adjustment, these experiences contribute to their professional growth and inform future instructional practices. By navigating such challenges, teachers gain valuable insights into supporting diverse learners in developing autonomy and responsibility.

2. Methodology

This study chapter introduced the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, credibility of the study, and ethical considerations. This study's investigation of facts and knowledge required subsequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions*—This study was based on the belief that individual experiences and perspectives shape knowledge. It followed an interpretive approach, focusing on how junior high school teachers experienced and applied self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms. The study assumed that these personal experiences were valuable and could not be fully understood through objective measures alone. It also recognized that the truth about teaching strategies varied from one teacher to another, depending on their unique experiences. Additionally, the study was guided by constructivism, which saw teachers as active, reflective practitioners who adapted their methods to improve student learning. This approach emphasized the importance of teachers’ reflections in developing effective strategies that empowered students to take control of their learning (Creswell Poth, 2018).

2.1.1. *Ontology*—The issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics. When researchers conduct qualitative research, they embrace the idea of analyzing Narratives of Junior High School Teachers on Self-Regulated Learning Strategies, as do the individuals being studied and the readers of a qualitative study. When

studying individuals, qualitative researchers intend to report multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes using multiple forms of evidence in themes, using the actual words of different individuals, and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently. According to Moustakas, as cited by Gabrielle (2023), phenomenology was chosen as the methodology for this study because it was “well suited to studying affective, emotional, and often intense human experience”. “The primary target of phenomenological knowledge is the understanding of meaningful, concrete relations implicit in the original description of experience in the context of a particular situation.” An ontology was a philosophical belief system about the nature of social reality, what can be known, and how. The conscious and unconscious questions, assumptions, and beliefs the researcher brings to the research endeavor are the initial basis for an ontological position. Ontological assumptions are fundamental beliefs about the nature of reality and human existence that underpin social research and policymaking (Newman, 2019).

2.1.2. *Epistemology*—Conducting a qualitative study means the researcher attempts to get as close as possible to the study participants. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. In this study, the researcher selected high school teachers as participants because they had known the researcher for quite a long time. Thus, the knowledge is gathered through the participants' subjective experiences. Conducting studies in the "field" where the participants live and work becomes essential, as these are vital contexts in understanding what the participants express. The longer researchers stay in the field or become familiar with the participants, the more they can "know what they know" through firsthand information. For instance, high-quality phenomenology requires a prolonged stay at the research site. Furthermore, the research was informed by the researchers' own experiences as social researchers working within interdisciplinary teams. Elsayah et al. (2020) contend that one of the main barriers to successful integrative research processes involves reconciling the epistemologies underpinning knowledge creation. Similarly, Moon et al. (2021) describe epistemology as the branch of philosophy that asks: How do we know what we know? It concerns ensuring that knowledge is adequate and legitimate by examining what constitutes a knowledge claim, including the assumptions made, how knowledge is produced or acquired, and determining how it can be applied.

2.1.3. *Axiology*—This assumption characterizes qualitative research. In practice, researchers conducting qualitative studies acknowledge the value-laden nature of the study and actively report their values and biases, as well as those embedded in the information gathered from the field. This study will share the findings with the school where the researcher was employed. The researcher intentionally positioned themselves within the study. For instance, in an interpretive biography, the re-

searcher's presence is evident in the text, and the author acknowledges that the narratives presented reflect both the subject's voice and the researcher's interpretive lens.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—This study assumed that teaching and learning experiences were complex, personal, and shaped by social interactions. Consistent with a qualitative approach, it viewed reality as constructed through individual perceptions rather than as an objective truth. By exploring the personal narratives of junior high school teachers, the study aimed to uncover deeper insights into how self-regulated learning strategies were applied in real classroom settings—insights that quantitative data alone might not have fully revealed (Creswell Poth, 2018). It also recognized that teaching experiences varied depending on context. In Davao City, student backgrounds, school resources, and education policies influenced how teachers implemented self-regulated learning. Understanding these local realities helped highlight the challenges and strategies unique to the area. Additionally, this study acknowledged that research interpretation was influenced by the participants' and the researcher's perspectives, making reflection an essential part of the qualitative process.

2.3. *Research Design*—The design of this study was qualitative, utilizing a narrative inquiry approach to explore the personal experiences of junior high school teachers in District 2, Cluster 14, Division of Davao City, regarding the application of self-regulated learning strategies in their teaching practices. Narrative inquiry was particularly well-suited for this study, as it enabled an in-depth exploration of how teachers understood and interpreted their experiences with self-regulated learning strategies, focusing on the meaning they attached to them and their impact on academic success. By collecting and analyzing teachers' stories, this study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of how these strategies were implemented in di-

verse classroom settings and how teachers navigated challenges and developed effective coping mechanisms to ensure their success in promoting student learning. The study employed purposive sampling to select participants who had experience applying self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms. Purposive sampling ensured that participants with rich, relevant experiences were chosen, thus providing valuable insights into the practical application of these strategies. The sample included junior high school teachers from various subjects and grade levels within District 2, ensuring a diversity of perspectives on how self-regulated learning was integrated into different educational contexts. Interviews were conducted with 10 teachers, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of their experiences. Data collection primarily involved semi-structured interviews, which were ideal for qualitative research as they offered flexibility in allowing participants to share their stories while guiding them to address specific research questions. The interviews took place either face-to-face or online, based on the participants' schedules and preferences. Each interview lasted approximately 45 to 60 minutes and focused on teachers' experiences applying self-regulated learning strategies, their challenges in implementing them, and the coping mechanisms they used to overcome obstacles. Additionally, field notes were taken during the interviews to capture nonverbal cues, contextual details, and any additional insights that informed the interpretation of the data. Thematic analysis was employed to identify patterns and themes in the interview data, understand the impact of self-regulated learning strategies on academic success, and provide a narrative-based understanding of how teachers implemented these strategies in their classrooms.

2.4. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations played a vital role in preserving this research's integrity and safeguarding the participants' rights. Since the study focused on the ex-

periences and viewpoints of junior high school teachers in District 2, Division of Davao City, concerning self-regulated learning strategies, addressing potential ethical issues during data collection and analysis was essential. These measures ensured the research was carried out responsibly and with transparency, protecting participants' autonomy, privacy, and welfare while adhering to the ethical principles of qualitative research.

2.4.1. Social Value—This research held significant social value by shedding light on the teaching practices of junior high school teachers, particularly their use of self-regulated learning strategies. The study aimed to identify effective strategies that could enhance students' academic performance and contribute to the professional development of teachers. The findings provided valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and school administrators in improving educational programs and teaching practices, ultimately benefiting the district's students and the broader educational community.

2.4.2. Informed Consent—In line with ethical guidelines, participants were fully informed about the nature, objectives, and scope of the research before they agreed to participate. The informed consent process involved providing participants with written consent forms clearly outlining their rights, including the option to participate voluntarily, the right to withdraw at any time, and protecting their confidentiality. Participants also had the opportunity to ask questions and seek clarification before signing the consent form, ensuring they fully understood their involvement in the study.

2.4.3. Vulnerability of Research Participants—While the study focused on experienced teachers, some participants may have felt vulnerable when discussing their teaching practices and challenges. To address this, the researcher created a supportive and non-judgmental environment that encouraged open dialogue. The researcher ensured that participants felt com-

comfortable sharing their experiences without fear of repercussions. The researcher also respected the participants' professional dignity throughout the research process, allowing them to reflect on their practices in a safe space. Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained to protect participants' identities and professional reputations. Additionally, participants were reminded that they could withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences, reinforcing their autonomy and agency.

2.4.4. Risks, Benefits, and Safety—The recruitment of participants was voluntary, and the researcher ensured that no undue pressure was applied. Interviews were conducted in a private and comfortable setting to minimize any risk of emotional or psychological harm. Participants were informed of the potential benefits of the study, including contributing to improving teaching practices and influencing educational policy. They were also reminded that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences.

2.4.5. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information—The study strictly adhered to the principles of privacy and confidentiality, as outlined in the Data Privacy Act of 2002. Identifying information was protected through pseudonyms and coded identifiers, ensuring that participants' identities remained anonymous. All data were securely stored and were only accessible to the researcher. The researcher took necessary precautions to ensure that any publications or reports from the study did not disclose personally identifiable information. Informed consent forms explicitly outlined how data would be handled, stored, and used, reinforcing transparency in the research process. Moreover, digital records were password-protected and regularly backed up to prevent unauthorized access or data loss.

2.4.6. Justice and Transparency—Participants were treated fairly and equitably throughout the study. They were informed of the re-

search process, their role in the study, and how their feedback would contribute to the findings. The researcher ensured transparency by providing participants access to the study results upon completion. If requested, participants also had the opportunity to review their interview transcripts and withdraw their data, if desired.

2.4.7. Qualification of the Researcher and Adequacy of Facilities—The researcher was well-qualified to conduct the study, having met all academic requirements and being familiar with qualitative research methods. The study was supported with appropriate resources, including access to necessary equipment, funding, and logistical support, to ensure the research was conducted with academic rigor and ethical integrity.

2.4.8. Community Involvement—The researcher respected the cultural norms and traditions of the District 2 community, ensuring that all participants felt valued and respected. The study did not involve deceptive practices, and participants were acknowledged for their contributions. The researcher maintained open lines of communication with the community throughout the study, fostering a collaborative relationship and ensuring that the research process was conducted transparently and respectfully.

2.4.9. Plagiarism and Fabrication—The researcher was committed to upholding academic integrity by ensuring that all sources were properly cited and that the research findings accurately reflected the participants' experiences. There was no fabrication or falsification of data, and the researcher ensured that the study was conducted with honesty and transparency, accurately representing the participants' voices (Creswell Creswell, 2022).

2.5. Research Participants—The participants in this study comprised ten (10) junior high school teachers, with two (2) teachers selected from each of the five schools in District II, Cluster XIV, of the Division of Davao City. The schools included in the study were Leon Gar-

cia National High School, Cabantian National High School, F. Bangoy National High School, Emilio Ramos National High School, and Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School. These schools were purposefully selected to ensure a diverse representation of teachers from various educational settings within the district. To qualify for participation, each teacher had to have at least 3 years of teaching experience, particularly in applying self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms. This criterion ensured that the participants possessed sufficient expertise to offer valuable, context-rich insights into their experiences with self-regulated learning practices. The sample included teachers from various subject areas and grade levels, ensuring a broad understanding of how self-regulated learning strategies were applied across different teaching contexts. This diversity was essential in capturing multiple perspectives on the impact of self-regulated learning strategies on teaching methods and student performance. Ten (10) participants were purposefully selected based on their experience and expertise in implementing these strategies, as their insights provided valuable information for the study. The teachers were invited to participate through official communication from the researcher, and informed consent was obtained prior to data collection. This selection process ensured that the study drew on the knowledge of experienced educators who were well-positioned to discuss the challenges, strategies, and insights related to self-regulated learning (Campbell et al., 2020; Ahmad Wilkins, 2024).

2.6. Research Instrument—This study used a researcher-made interview guide to collect qualitative data from junior high school teachers in District 2, Davao City. The interview guide was designed to explore the self-regulated learning strategies employed by these teachers in their classrooms, focusing on how they implemented them and the challenges they faced. The guide was carefully developed to

align with the research objectives and was validated through expert consultation to ensure the clarity and relevance of the questions. Experts reviewed the guide to confirm that the language was appropriate for the participants' professional background. The questions effectively addressed the study's focus on self-regulated learning strategies in junior high school settings. This validation process ensured that the interview guide was both conceptually sound and capable of generating meaningful data (Creswell Creswell, 2022). The questions were designed to allow participants to express their personal experiences in implementing self-regulated learning strategies. Open-ended questions were included to encourage participants to share in-depth narratives of their practices, challenges, and perceptions. This approach allowed the researcher to capture rich, descriptive data that reflected the teachers' perspectives on fostering self-regulation in their students. As qualitative research prioritized understanding over generalization, the semi-structured format of the interview guide offered flexibility, enabling the researcher to explore emergent themes and insights that may not have been anticipated initially. A pilot test was conducted with a small group of teachers to identify issues with question clarity or wording, allowing for refinement before the full study. This process ensured the final interview guide was reliable, effective, and suitable for gathering the required data from teachers in Davao City (Creswell Creswell, 2022).

2.7. Role of the Researcher—In this study, the researcher assumed several critical roles to ensure the research process was conducted with integrity, rigor, and clarity. These roles were pivotal in guiding the study from design to conclusion, ensuring the research was ethically sound and methodologically rigorous.

2.7.1. Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research—The researcher served as a facilitator, guiding the participants through the

interview process to ensure the collection of valid and meaningful data. The researcher was responsible for maintaining a neutral tone and avoiding introducing bias into the conversations. The researcher actively promoted an environment where participants felt comfortable sharing their perspectives and refrained from imposing personal views during data collection. The researcher allowed the data to emerge naturally from the participants' experiences by remaining impartial and open-minded. Clarifying questions were used to deepen understanding without leading participants toward specific responses. The researcher also maintained detailed field notes to capture non-verbal cues and contextual details that enriched data interpretation. Continuous reflection and adherence to ethical standards ensured that the researcher's presence did not influence the authenticity of participant responses. The researcher's role as a neutral facilitator was crucial to maintaining the integrity of the qualitative research process (Creswell Creswell, 2022).

2.7.2. Expert in Qualitative Method—The researcher applied their knowledge of qualitative research methodologies to ensure the study was conducted precisely. This included expertise in conducting interviews, transcribing data, and employing methods like Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis to analyze the collected data. The researcher rigorously followed qualitative research protocols, engaged in self-reflection, and sought guidance from experienced mentors and research advisors to ensure that the study's design, data collection, and analysis remained robust. The researcher's role as an expert guided the research toward valid, reliable, and meaningful findings grounded in the participants' experiences.

2.7.3. Collector and Keeper of Data—As the primary collector and keeper of data, the researcher handled the data with the utmost care and responsibility. The researcher ensured that all audio, video, or written data were collected

securely and stored to maintain confidentiality and protect participant privacy. Audio or video recordings of interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were transcribed verbatim and stored securely. The researcher also outlined clear data management procedures to protect participants' identities and sensitive information. This role was fundamental to the study's ethical integrity and credibility.

2.7.4. Analyst of Data—After data collection, the researcher assumed the analyst role, carefully reviewing and interpreting the data. This involved coding the responses and identifying recurring themes or patterns from the interviews and discussions. The researcher applied an interpretive approach, seeking to understand the data from the participants' perspectives rather than imposing preconceived interpretations. Thematic analysis explored how the themes aligned with the research questions, ensuring the findings reflected the participants' lived experiences. In this phase, the researcher ensured the analysis was rigorous and representative of the participants' voices (Creswell Creswell, 2022).

2.7.5. Organizer and Presenter of Data—Finally, the researcher took on the role of organizer and presenter, structuring the findings clearly and cohesively. The data were presented around the central themes identified during analysis, ensuring that each research question was addressed in detail. The researcher also reflected on the implications of the findings, offering recommendations for educational practice and policy. These findings were aimed at enhancing literacy and numeracy instruction and suggested areas for future research. By organizing and presenting the findings in an accessible and engaging way, the researcher helped ensure that the study contributed valuable insights to the field.

2.8. Data Collection—The data collection process for this study was conducted systematically and ethically, ensuring transparency, valid-

ity, and respect for the participants' rights. The entire process was carried out in several stages, as outlined below: Initial Preparations and Obtaining Required Documents. The researcher first obtained an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School, Dr. Nelia G. Aga. The document demonstrated the study's ethical soundness and institutional support. Seeking Permission from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS). After securing the necessary institutional endorsements, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division of Davao City, Reynante A. Solitario, to conduct the research in selected schools within Cluster 14. The researcher submitted a formal letter requesting approval to conduct the study, along with the Ethics Certificate, endorsement letter from the Dean, Chapters 1 and 2 of the research, and the interview guide to be used in the study. These documents were reviewed to ensure the study aligned with division policies and research standards. Seeking Permission from the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS). Upon receiving the approved letter from the Division Office, the researcher sought permission from the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) assigned to Cluster 14. The documents, including the approved division letter, were submitted to the PSDS to endorse the study within the cluster's schools formally. Securing Permission from School Heads. After obtaining the necessary approvals from the Division Office and PSDS, the researcher sought permission from the school heads of the identified junior high schools in District 2, Davao City. A formal letter was sent to each principal, outlining the study's purpose, procedures, and the role of teachers in the research. This step ensured support from school leadership and informed the teachers about their voluntary participation. The support of the school heads was crucial for the smooth implementation of the research process. Obtaining Consent from Participants. Once the school heads granted permission, the researcher conducted a formal orientation with the selected participants. The study's objectives, procedures, and potential risks were explained in detail during the orientation. Emphasis was placed on the voluntary nature of participation. Each participant was provided with an informed consent form, which included assurances of confidentiality and anonymity. Participants were reminded of their right to withdraw from the study without facing any negative consequences. The entire consent process was conducted ethically to ensure that participants fully understood their rights and the scope of their involvement (Creswell Creswell, 2022). Conducting the Interview. The researcher conducted individual, in-depth interviews with the selected participants using the researcher-made interview guide. Each participant's profile was documented, and the interviews were audio-recorded with the participants' consent to ensure accurate transcription. The researcher created a comfortable interview environment, fostering open dialogue and ensuring participants felt comfortable sharing their experiences. Throughout the interview, the researcher remained neutral, avoided influencing the participants' responses, and ensured their voices were authentically represented. Transcribing Interview Responses and Data Coding. After the interviews, the researcher transcribed the audio recordings verbatim, ensuring that every response was accurately captured. Since some participants spoke vernacular, the researcher translated their responses into English to maintain consistency and clarity during the data analysis phase. Once transcribed, the data were categorized and coded to identify recurring themes and patterns in the responses. Thematic analysis was conducted to uncover commonalities and differences across participants, which helped address the research questions. The coded data were then analyzed to better understand the self-regulated learning strategies junior high school teachers in District 2, Davao City, used. The researcher also

used memo writing during the coding process to document emerging insights and potential interpretations. Codes were continuously refined and organized into broader thematic categories to enhance analytic depth. To ensure credibility, the researcher conducted a peer debriefing process, where another qualitative researcher reviewed the coding scheme and interpretations

2.9. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was employed to analyze the data gathered from the interviews, using Creswell’s Model for qualitative research as a guiding framework (Creswell Creswell, 2022). The researcher used thematic analysis to detect, examine, and present recurring patterns (themes) found in the data, offering a comprehensive understanding of junior high school teachers’ self-regulated learning strategies in Davao City. These themes represented the core ideas and insights shared by the participants during the interviews, providing a structured approach to data interpretation. The process began with familiarization with the data, where the researcher immersed herself in the transcriptions by reading and re-reading them multiple times. This initial step ensured that the researcher thoroughly understood the responses, noting explicit insights and the underlying meanings in the participants’ narratives. This stage was crucial to ensure sensitivity to the nuances of the data, fostering a deeper understanding of the teachers’ experiences with self-regulated learning strategies. Next, the researcher proceeded to coding, which involved breaking down the data into smaller, meaningful segments. Relevant features related to the research questions were identified and labeled. The coding process captured semantic content (explicit ideas directly stated by participants) and latent meanings (underlying or implicit ideas that reflected deeper insights). These codes were organized systematically, enabling the researcher to categorize them into themes aligned with the study’s objectives. Following the coding, the researcher searched for themes

by clustering related codes into coherent groups representing recurring patterns or ideas. These themes were refined during the reviewing phase, where the researcher ensured that each theme accurately reflected the data and aligned with the research questions. This iterative process ensured the clarity and consistency of the themes, making certain they were accurate and interrelated in a way that told a logical story about the teachers’ strategies for self-regulation in the classroom. In the defining and naming phase, the researcher articulated the essence of each theme, clearly defining its meaning and assigning a descriptive name that succinctly captured its significance. This phase ensured the themes were easily understandable and reflected the participants’ experiences. Finally, during the writing-up phase, the researcher integrated the themes into a comprehensive narrative, presenting the findings in a way that wove together the teachers’ voices with the existing literature. This narrative linked the results to the broader context of self-regulated learning, providing insights into how junior high school teachers in Davao City employed self-regulated learning strategies to enhance student learning. This structured approach to thematic analysis ensured that the study offered a robust, reflective analysis that highlighted the depth and breadth of the teachers’ experiences. The final narrative aimed to preserve the authenticity of participants’ lived experiences while drawing meaningful connections to theoretical perspectives and current educational practices.

2.10. Analytical Framework—The analytical framework for this study adopted the framework analysis method to systematically examine the qualitative data while allowing flexibility throughout the analysis process. This approach, proposed by Stalmeijer (2023), provided the researcher with the option to analyze data concurrently with its collection or to perform the analysis after all data had been gathered. The process comprised five distinct steps: familiarization,

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

thematic framework identification, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation. Each step was designed to organize, classify, and interpret the data to ensure alignment with the study’s objectives, which explored the self-regulated learning strategies of junior high school teachers in Davao City. The first phase, familiarization, was foundational to the analytical process. During this phase, the researcher immersed herself in the collected data through interviews, field notes, or any other qualitative materials, thoroughly reviewing the data to understand its content comprehensively. Key ideas, patterns,

and recurrent themes emerged during this phase. Because the data was extensive, reviewing everything in detail was impractical. Hence, the researcher focused on a representative portion of the data, ensuring that the analysis was balanced and covered all collection methods. The next stage, thematic framework identification, involved identifying emerging themes and key issues from the data. While certain themes were anticipated based on the study’s objectives, the researcher remained open to new themes that naturally arose.

These themes were grouped and organized into a framework that helped filter and classify the data for further analysis. This allowed the researcher to ensure that the data was interpreted in a way that stayed true to the participants’ voices and experiences. Following the thematic framework identification were the steps of indexing and charting. The researcher tagged specific data sections corresponding to the identified themes in the indexing phase. This involved coding the data using numerical systems or software tools to streamline the process. In the charting phase, the indexed data was reor-

ganized into visual formats, such as charts or diagrams, reflecting key themes and patterns. These visual representations helped synthesize the data and made the thematic analysis more accessible and clearer. Finally, the mapping and interpretation phase involved synthesizing the findings into coherent schemas. This stage focuses on interpreting the data by defining concepts, identifying associations, and formulating recommendations or strategies based on the participants’ experiences and beliefs. It served as the culmination of the analysis, where the researcher combined all the insights from the

data into a comprehensive understanding of the self-regulated learning strategies employed by junior high school teachers in Davao City. By following this structured yet adaptable framework, the researcher ensured a rigorous and transparent analysis. This approach allowed for an in-depth exploration of the participants' experiences while remaining aligned with the research objectives, ultimately providing a rich understanding of self-regulated learning strategies in the context of Davao City's junior high school teachers.

2.11. Trustworthiness of the Study—In qualitative research, trustworthiness was essential for ensuring the rigor and integrity of the findings. Unlike quantitative research, which emphasized validity and reliability, qualitative studies focused on credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability as core indicators of trustworthiness. These elements collectively ensured that the study's findings were robust, relevant, and rooted in the participants' experiences. The credibility of this study was ensured by accurately capturing and representing the participants' perspectives. The researcher conducted in-depth, semi-structured interviews with junior high school teachers in Davao City to enhance credibility. This allowed for a deep and nuanced understanding of their self-regulated learning strategies. Additionally, data saturation was used as a benchmark to determine when further interviews would no longer yield new insights. This process helped ensure that the study reflected the full scope of the participants' experiences, making the findings authentic and reliable. Transferability describes how well the study's findings can be relevant or applicable to different settings

or groups. This study enhanced transferability by providing a rich and detailed description of the research context of junior high school teachers in Davao City and the research methodology, including how data were collected and analyzed. By documenting the specific conditions, settings, and processes, the researcher allowed future scholars or practitioners to assess whether the study's findings could be applied to similar educational contexts or regions. This transparency supported the broader relevance of the study's conclusions. Dependability emphasized the consistency and repeatability of the research process. To ensure dependability, the researcher employed an external evaluator who reviewed the study's methodology, data collection, and analysis processes. This external review ensured that the research methods were applied consistently and that the findings were aligned with the data. Additionally, the researcher meticulously documented every process stage, facilitating replication under similar conditions. This attention to detail strengthened the study's consistency and the findings' reliability. Confirmability ensured that the participants' experiences shaped the findings rather than the researcher's biases or preconceptions. The researcher ensured confirmability by maintaining detailed documentation and conducting member checks with participants throughout the study. By returning the findings to participants for validation, the researcher confirmed that the interpretations of their responses accurately reflected their views and experiences. Regular checks for potential researcher bias also contributed to the study's objectivity, confirming that the findings were based on the data rather than subjective interpretation.

3. Results and Discussion

This study section answers the research questions based on participant feedback. The investigation explored the personal experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of junior high school teachers, as well as their insights into applying, implementing, and the effectiveness of Self-

Regulated Learning strategies.

3.1. *Personal Experiences of Junior High School Teachers in Applying Self-Regulated Learning Strategies*—Junior high school teacher's personal experiences as self-regulated learners significantly influence their teaching, especially when implementing SRL strategies. Teachers often favor strategies they find compelling in their learning, with past successes or failures shaping their confidence in their abilities. Furthermore, teachers are vital in fostering students' metacognitive development by offering guidance, encouraging reflection, and providing chances for self-evaluation. Fujita et al. (2021) reported that junior high school teachers in Japan expressed concerns about their effectiveness in teaching. They questioned whether their students possessed the motivation, perseverance, and emotional intelligence to study independently with reduced supervision. Meanwhile, self-directed learning among junior high educators has been shown to boost their confidence and enhance their adaptability, ultimately improving their teaching effectiveness (Alshaikhi, 2020).

3.1.1. *Managed Time Efficiently*—Participants shared meaningful experiences on gradually learning to manage time efficiently while implementing self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies in their classrooms. Over time, they became more adept at incorporating activities such as goal-setting, journaling, and reflection within the constraints of the school schedule (Artino Stephens, 2020). Through thoughtful adjustments, they discovered that even brief yet consistent SRL routines could be seamlessly embedded into lessons without disrupting content flow. These experiences highlighted how deliberate time management supported their teaching goals and helped their students become more organized, focused, and independent in managing their academic responsibilities. Under the "Manage Time Efficiently" sub-theme, partici-

pants highlighted how integrating self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies within a tight academic schedule required careful planning, creativity, and adaptation—an experience consistent with recent findings that SRL implementation must be flexible and context-responsive to be effective (Dignath Veenman, 2021; Michalsky, 2020). Despite the initial challenges, teachers effectively balanced instructional time with self-regulated learning (SRL) practices. Participant 5 (P5) admitted that time management was initially a significant concern when incorporating SRL strategies like journaling, goal-setting, and peer feedback. These activities, although valuable, were perceived as detracting from core content delivery. However, through reflective practice, P5 innovated by embedding brief SRL routines, such as short goal-setting exercises at the beginning of the lesson and quick reflections at the end of the lesson. This adaptive strategy enabled teachers to maintain content coverage while fostering students' self-regulation skills (Panadero, 2017; Artino Stephens, 2020). Participant 6 (P6) echoed similar concerns about curriculum time constraints, noting that the pressure to meet content deadlines sometimes tempted them to skip reflective or goal-setting sessions. However, they found that even small windows of time, such as five-minute end-of-class reflections, had a significant impact on students' learning behaviors. This response underscores how even micro-interventions can support SRL without heavily disrupting the lesson flow (Theobald, 2022). Participant 4 (P4) approached time management from the learners' perspective, observing how SRL tools, such as planners, checklists, and deadlines, improved students' organizational skills. These tools empowered students to plan, prioritize tasks, and track their progress, resulting in fewer missed deadlines and more effective time management (Wong et al., 2023). The teacher promoted

learner autonomy by equipping learners with these tools while optimizing classroom time. Participant 10 (P10) emphasized that SRL activities such as peer feedback and goal-setting initially posed time constraints. However, similar to P5 and P6, they discovered that these strategies could be smoothly integrated into existing lesson structures. Starting a lesson with a quick goal-setting prompt and ending with brief reflective exercises has become a time-efficient way to foster Self-Regulated Learning (SRL). This practice reflects a deliberate balance between content delivery and skill development, showing that SRL does not necessarily require extra time but thoughtful integration (Dignath, 2021; Zimmerman Schunk, 2011). The narrative above highlights the personal view of junior high school teachers' lived experiences integrating Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) strategies into a curriculum with tight time constraints. Teachers initially worried incorporating activities like journaling, goal-setting, and peer feedback would sacrifice content coverage. However, they discovered that these strategies could be integrated more naturally and efficiently, such as using brief goal-setting at the start of lessons and short reflections at the end (Zimmerman, 2021). To manage time efficiently while implementing self-regulated learning strategies, junior high school teachers reported utilizing structured schedules, allocating classroom responsibilities strategically, and incorporating digital tools to simplify lesson delivery and student engagement (König, Jäger-Biela, Glutsch, 2020). These practices helped maximize instructional time and maintain focus on learning objectives. Through consistent application of self-regulation techniques in their teaching routines, educators could also model and instill these habits in their students. Research underscores the importance of academic time management as a foundational component of effective learning. It is recognized as a planning behavior that correlates with an individual's perception of

the effort needed to meet academic challenges and is enhanced by motivation and goal-setting (Casiraghi, Di Gioia, Pinardi, 2020). Furthermore, complementary learning strategies must support effective time management, including self-assessment, content organization, information seeking, self-monitoring, help-seeking behaviors, and regular review—skills essential for academic success (Broadbent Poon, 2020).

3.1.2. Fostered Innovation—Fostered Innovation highlights the creative and adaptive approaches junior high school teachers employ in integrating self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies into their classroom practice. Faced with shifting student interests, technological distractions, and the demands of a tight curriculum, teachers were willing to experiment with new methods that encouraged learner independence, engagement, and critical thinking—precisely the kind of contextual Innovation recent research describes as essential for SRL success in real-world settings (Dignath Veenman, 2021). Innovation was reflected in contextualized instruction and real-life applications, along with a gradual release of responsibility to students, fostering autonomy and ownership of learning. Through strategies such as collaborative learning, graphic organizers, reflective journaling, and group projects, teachers adapted traditional practices to suit the evolving needs of 21st-century learners. Studies confirm that graphic organizers enhance SRL by promoting conceptual understanding and critical thinking in classroom contexts (Chularut DeBacker, 2021), while reflective journaling and collaborative work support metacognitive awareness and engagement among students Greenquist-Marlett et al. (2024). This innovation process catalyzed the promotion of SRL, ultimately empowering students to become more self-directed and motivated in their academic journeys. Under the theme “Fostered Innovation,” participants demonstrated various creative and adaptive strategies in implementing self-regulated

learning (SRL) in response to the evolving needs of their students and the classroom context. Participant 1 (P1) emphasized the importance of contextualized learning and real-life applications, suggesting that meaningful learning occurs when lessons are grounded in students' lived experiences. This is supported by Hilongos and Casinillo (2024), who emphasized that contextualized instruction, combined with the Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR) model, enhances learner autonomy and promotes Self-Regulated Learning (SRL). The teacher applied the GRR model, which transitions learning ownership from the teacher to the student (Hilongos Casinillo, 2024). Furthermore, P1 highlighted the role of collaborative learning, an innovative pedagogical approach that promotes peer interaction while integrating Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) principles into authentic, real-life scenarios—a connection reinforced by Rosário et al. (2023), who emphasized collaboration as a pathway to active engagement and metacognitive development. Participant 3 (P3) reflected on the shifting landscape of student interests, particularly the reduced motivation for traditional activities like writing on paper due to increased gadget use. Instead of resisting these changes, P3 implied the need to innovate by acknowledging students' digital tendencies and possibly integrating SRL tools and strategies that align with their tech-savvy behaviors. Munshi et al. (2022) support this, arguing that technology-enhanced adaptive scaffolding fosters self-regulated learning (SRL) by responding to students' digital learning preferences. Participant 4 (P4) fostered innovation by simplifying the introduction of SRL through the use of graphic organizers. This low-cost yet highly effective visual tool enabled students to organize their thoughts better, promoting metacognition and independence in managing their tasks. Research by Frontiers in Psychology (Rosário et al., 2023) supports the use of such tools to scaffold self-regulated learning (SRL) processes, such as planning, monitoring, and evaluation. Participant 7 (P7) suggested using reflective journals to deepen student understanding and enhance critical thinking. Encouraging students to reflect on their learning experiences is a cognitive and emotional strategy that supports Self-Regulated Learning (SRL). As noted by Rosário et al. (2023), structured reflection enables learners to develop metacognitive awareness and personal accountability. Participant 10 (P10) described how students' dependence on the teacher for directions prompted the implementation of SRL through goal-setting, monitoring, and group-based reflection. This innovation was driven by a real classroom need: helping students become less reliant and more proactive. This aligns with Hilongos and Casinillo (2024), who found that even structured SRL micro-strategies embedded in routine instruction can promote student autonomy and academic responsibility. Junior high teachers play a crucial role in fostering innovation by integrating self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies into their practice. Whether through explicit teaching or task design, this approach cultivates independent learners. By developing metacognition, motivation, and strategic action, students are better equipped to succeed academically and personally. Innovation in education means solving a real problem in a new, simple way that promotes fair and equitable learning. (Strengthening education systems and innovation UNICEF, (2022). It seems most useful to consider pedagogical innovation as a process rather than an outcome and innovative teachers as people who engage in that process Gilbert et al., (2020). The narratives shared by participants during the in-depth interviews in fostering innovation through self-regulated learning (SRL). They highlight the importance of contextualized learning, real-life applications, and the Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR) model to empower students to take ownership of their learning. Recognizing students' preference for technology

over traditional writing, they introduce SRL strategies with simple tools like graphic organizers and advocate for reflective journals to enhance critical thinking. Hence, their motivation stems from observing students' over-reliance on teacher guidance and a desire to cultivate independent learners who can set goals, monitor progress, and reflect on their learning, often through collaborative projects. As supported by Nugraha (2022), the changes in the world of education can be observed through the emergence of various innovations in the education system, learning implementation, educational media, and matters related to the educational realm. For changes that occur in the curriculum, teachers must be able to adapt learning principles to the assessment process, as well as foster good cooperation between students, teachers, and parents so that curriculum implementation can run optimally (Megandarisari, 2021). Similarly, as students offer innovative ideas throughout the program, it suggests a shift in their attitudes, which begins to foster the courage to innovate. This gradual shift indicates that SRL not only improves academic outcomes but also nurtures creativity and initiative among learners. As teachers observe these changes, they are further encouraged to refine their strategies, knowing that fostering innovation starts with empowering students to regulate their own learning processes.

3.1.3. Lack of Students' Engagement — Many junior high school classrooms struggle with student engagement, even though it is critical for achieving meaningful learning outcomes. Students often disengage when lessons do not connect to their real-world problems, interests, or learning preferences. Integrating self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies has shown promise in boosting both engagement and comprehension. For example, a study by Hong, Xie, and Yang (2022) found that higher levels of SRL were significantly associated with increased perceived academic control and ac-

tive online learning engagement among junior high school students. When students can see how scientific principles apply in everyday contexts and when teachers tailor instruction to individual needs—using materials that spark inquiry and collaboration—the focus shifts from rote memorization to critical thinking, facilitated by metacognitive strategies such as questioning the “why” and “how” of learning. Encouraging students to self-evaluate further promotes progress monitoring. Additionally, immersive tools such as interactive virtual labs in science education support Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) by enabling planning, monitoring, and self-reflection during hands-on activities, which in turn enhances engagement across behavioral, cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions (Alzahrani Lähtevänoja, 2023). Together, these approaches create active and enthusiastic classrooms where learning is not just received but owned by the students. Participant2(P2) emphasized that self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies cater to learners' diverse needs. According to this teacher, when students are more engaged, it indicates that the approach being used is practical. This perspective emphasizes the direct connection between meaningful engagement and the thoughtful application of SRL strategies, where learners assume greater ownership of their progress. This aligns with the findings of Xu, Zhang, and Maeda (2023), who concluded that SRL strategies significantly enhance learner motivation and performance across various modalities. Participant3(P3) pointed out that real-life applications of science concepts have the potential to influence students even beyond the four walls of the classroom. This response highlights how practical and relevant lessons can enhance engagement by demonstrating the value and utility of learning in everyday life, a key principle in fostering self-regulation (Nemati et al., 2024). Participant6(P6) noted the importance of considering learners' needs and selecting appropri-

ate learning activities. With the abundance of online resources, the teacher emphasized the importance of teachers selecting the resources that best fit their students. This demonstrates that engagement begins with planning—aligning SRL strategies and materials to student’s unique interests and abilities, as supported by Hong, Xie, and Yang (2022), who found that perceived academic control and strategic alignment increase learning engagement in SRL settings. As Participant7(P7) pointed out, students can tailor their learning and gain a more thorough comprehension by employing metacognitive tactics. Instead of memorizing facts and figures, students actively consider the “why” and “how” behind what they learn, boosting their cognitive engagement and retention. Xu et al. (2023) emphasized that metacognitive strategies within SRL frameworks are strong predictors of deeper learning and sustained engagement. Participant9(P9) emphasized the significance of self-evaluation in assisting students in identifying their strengths and areas for improvement. Engaged, self-regulated learners exhibit qualities such as academic responsibility and self-awareness, which are fostered through this practice. This insight aligns with the findings of Nemati et al. (2024), who demonstrated a connection between self-monitoring and evaluation and increased academic persistence and responsibility. Finally, Participant10(P10) recommended visually stimulating and dynamic virtual experiments to enhance recall and engagement. Students are more likely to remember material and stay engaged when classes are interactive and visually engaging. This response illustrates how inventive methods of capturing students’ attention can address disengagement, aligning with the findings of Ernita et al. (2024), who discovered that virtual labs enhance both critical thinking and self-regulated learning (SRL) behaviors in STEM students. The participants’ responses during the in-depth-interview expressed their ideas that self-regulated learn-

ing enhances engagement and academic performance by catering to diverse student needs. Real-life applications of science concepts extend learning beyond the classroom, making it more impactful. Teachers must carefully select activities that align with students’ needs, ensuring effective integration. Metacognitive strategies foster a deeper understanding, while self-assessment enables students to evaluate their capabilities. Visuals and virtual experiments aid retention, making complex ideas easier to grasp. Junior high school teachers encounter difficulties implementing self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies due to low student engagement. This disengagement can stem from a lack of interest or motivation, or students not seeing the relevance of the material. Furthermore, some teachers may lack the necessary training and support to apply SRL techniques effectively. The classroom environment, individual student needs, and even a teacher’s personal views on SRL can also influence the success of implementing these strategies. SRL research shows how teacher instructional practices that promote SRL (e.g., choice, self-assessment) empower students to take up learning opportunities, leading to an increase in engagement and quality of learning outcomes (Perry et al., 2020), and connect with students’ community and cultural backgrounds are associated with their engagement, as Gray et al. (2020) added.

3.1.4. Problem-Solved through Practical Activities—Teachers may encounter initial challenges when implementing self-regulated learning (SRL) practices, particularly when faced with time constraints, curriculum pressures, or uncertainty about where to start. However, many of these issues are gradually addressed through practical, classroom-based activities. Graphic organizers have been shown to promote metacognitive regulation and enhance conceptual understanding, particularly when integrated into self-regulated learning (SRL) routines (Robillos, 2023). Likewise, tools such as

mini-goal templates and checklists help scaffold student planning and monitoring, making SRL strategies more manageable for both learners and teachers (Xu, Zhang, Maeda, 2023). Reflection journals are also effective in deepening students' metacognitive engagement and emotional connection to learning, contributing significantly to improved academic outcomes (Chang Lin, 2023). Teachers reported that embedding these SRL strategies into regular classroom activities—rather than isolating them as separate lessons—encouraged greater student ownership and autonomy (Greenquist-Marlett et al., 2024). These hands-on approaches not only addressed instructional challenges but also cultivated learners who are more independent, reflective, and actively engaged with their academic growth. Participant 1 observed that self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies significantly improved students' independence and responsibility. Providing tools like goal-setting, progress tracking, and self-reflection empowered learners to own their academic journeys. This aligns with findings by Munshi et al. (2022), who demonstrated that adaptive scaffolds in science contexts enhance students' metacognitive regulation and autonomy, and Makiaway et al. (2024), whose study reported an 83% increase in student ownership. Participant 6 turned to concrete visual aids—using graphic organizers for planning and “mini-goals” for sessions. These practical tools support intentional thinking and make SRL actionable. Robillos (2023) found that digital graphic organizers bolster metacognitive task structuring, while Munshi et al. (2022) documented similar improvements in performance clarity via strategy scaffolds. Participant 9 initially struggled with time constraints for teaching SRL explicitly. This issue was resolved by integrating SRL strategies into routine classroom activities, rather than isolating them. Research shows that embedding SRL into daily lesson flow leads to sustained engagement and ease of implementation (Munshi et al., 2022; Makiaway et al., 2024).

Participant 10 emphasized reflective journals, checklists, and rubrics, noting how they develop metacognition, self-awareness, and self-regulation. Chang and Lin (2023) reported a large effect ($g = 0.79$) of structured reflection on motivation and SRL strategy use, while Makiaway et al. (2024) underscored how reflective journaling enhances students' insight into challenges and learning strategies. Participant 3 admitted feeling unprepared to teach SRL initially. Their confidence and effectiveness grew significantly after attending a professional development workshop. This underscores the vital role of teacher training in SRL implementation, consistent with insights from Munshi et al. (2022) that guided scaffolding and teacher readiness are key for translating SRL into classroom practice. The narratives shared by participants P1, P6, P9, P10, and P3 during the in-depth interviews revealed their thoughts on integrated Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) through the use of goal-setting, tracking, and reflection tools. Visual aids, such as graphic organizers and mini-goal templates, effectively facilitated learning. Embedding SRL into regular classroom activities—rather than presenting it as a separate lesson—emerged as a key “problem solved.” Participants also emphasized the importance of tools such as self-reflection journals, checklists, and rubrics in supporting students' metacognitive development. Additionally, several teachers emphasized the need for professional development, such as workshops and training sessions, to overcome their initial unpreparedness in implementing SRL effectively. Junior high school teachers' personal experiences with applying SRL strategies revealed a mix of challenges and meaningful opportunities for professional growth and enhanced student performance. The effective use of SRL—particularly strategies such as self-monitoring, goal-setting, and self-instruction—depends on a range of instructional methods and teacher beliefs. Vosniadou et al. (2020) found that teachers often

hold varied and sometimes conflicting beliefs about Self-Regulated Learning (SRL), which can either support or hinder its integration into daily instruction. These beliefs shape instructional choices and influence whether SRL is treated as a core pedagogical approach or as an optional add-on. Cheng (2011) emphasized that core SRL strategies, such as goal-setting, motivation, and action control, are closely linked to improved academic performance. This reinforces the findings of this study, which show that teachers noticed increased student engagement and independence when students were guided to set goals, track progress, and reflect on their learning processes. Tools such as goal trackers and reflection logs played a central role in this transformation. Finally, Dignath and Büttner (2021) concluded in their meta-analysis that professional development programs significantly enhance the successful application of self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies in classrooms. Their findings support the participants' suggestions that teacher training and support structures are essential for the long-term integration of SRL. Without adequate professional preparation, the implementation of SRL tends to be inconsistent, limiting its potential impact on

student learning outcomes. While some of these beliefs align with core SRL principles—such as viewing learning as a constructive process or recognizing SRL's potential to improve academic outcomes—they significantly influence how teachers value and adopt SRL-based instructional strategies in the classroom. Figure 3 provides a compelling glimpse into the personal experiences of junior high school teachers as they navigate the implementation of self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms. The data highlights a mixed bag of outcomes, with some teachers successfully fostering innovation and teaching students to manage their time efficiently. However, the figure also reveals significant challenges, particularly the persistent issue of student disengagement, which teachers report as a significant barrier to the practical application of these strategies. However, the ability of students to independently problem-solve, a key component of self-regulated learning, appears to be another area where teachers encounter difficulties, suggesting that while the intention to promote these skills is present, the practical application and student uptake are not consistently successful.

3.2. Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Implementing Self-Regulated Learning Strategies and Their Coping Mechanisms—Key challenges for teachers implementing self-regulated learning (SRL) include limited knowledge of SRL's effectiveness, time constraints, and the need for professional development. Teachers cope by engaging teachers' adaptability and flexibility, ensuring students' participation, and achieving effective resolutions with a growth mindset regarding teaching and student learning.

3.2.1. Teachers' Adaptability and Flexibility—Teachers' adaptation and flexibility are critical in successfully incorporating self-

regulated learning (SRL) into classroom instruction. As educators navigate diverse student needs, shifting educational contexts, and evolving learning environments, their ability to adjust instructional strategies becomes key to fostering autonomy. According to Faith and Pyle (2021), highly effective SRL implementation relies on planned instructional change, where teachers adaptively scaffold SRL elements—such as goal-setting and metacognitive reflection—into daily instruction. Similarly, Sáez-Delgado et al. (2022) emphasize that when teachers personalize SRL approaches and respond to individual student needs, learners are more likely to develop ownership of their

Fig. 3. Personal Experiences of Junior High School Teachers in Applying Self-Regulated Learning Strategies

learning process. Through strategies such as reflective practices, real-world applications, and differentiated support, flexible teachers help promote independent and engaged learners, reinforcing Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) both inside and beyond the classroom. Participant 2 (P2) highlighted the importance of connecting scientific concepts to real-world applications as a flexible approach to fostering engagement and motivation. The participant explained that when students see the relevance of topics like solar energy in practical contexts, such as renewable technologies or environmental careers, it encourages deeper interest and a broader understanding beyond classroom requirements. This aligns with the findings of Grover et al. (2022), who emphasized that real-world and citizen science tasks promote deeper student engagement and relevance. Similarly, Rutten et al. (2022) demonstrated that simulation-based activities in science learning increase students' motivation and comprehension when grounded in real-life contexts. Participant 4 (P4) emphasized the need for a gradual and patient approach to building student independence through self-regulation. The participant noted that starting with small steps, such as guided practice in

setting goals, allows students to develop the confidence and skills to manage their learning gradually. This method aligns with the findings of Alvi and Gillies (2021), who emphasized that scaffolded goal-setting and structured metacognitive guidance facilitate the progressive development of SRL skills. Panadero et al. (2023) also stressed the importance of pacing instruction based on students' readiness levels to ensure the successful adoption of self-regulated learning (SRL) behaviors. Participant 7 (P7) noted that self-regulated learning equips learners with essential life skills, including taking initiative, reflecting on their actions, and adapting their approaches. This perspective aligns with the research of Feraco et al. (2022), who found that SRL promotes adaptability, resilience, and reflective thinking—competencies that extend beyond academic contexts. Likewise, Guo (2022) emphasized that teaching SRL cultivates long-term learner flexibility and independent decision-making skills. Participant 9 (P9) briefly but meaningfully noted that tutoring served as an effective intervention to support SRL. This approach reflects the teacher's ability to address students' varied learning needs by tailoring instruction with individualized sup-

port. Xu, Zhang, and Maeda (2023) confirmed that personalized SRL strategies—such as one-on-one scaffolding—can significantly enhance learning outcomes, especially for students who initially struggle with independent learning. Callan and Shim (2019) also emphasized the need for individualized approaches to ensure equitable self-regulated learning (SRL) development. The participants' narratives during the in-depth interviews highlighted that real-world applications of scientific concepts, such as understanding solar energy, can leave a lasting impact on students by inspiring them to adopt sustainable practices or pursue careers in green energy. As a junior high school teacher, they believe in starting with small, patient steps to foster independence. For instance, structured guidance in goal-setting should be provided before gradually encouraging students to set their own goals. This method enables students to cultivate initiative, engage in self-reflection, and apply their skills to situations beyond the classroom. Additionally, tutoring has proven to be an effective intervention in promoting self-regulated learning, further supporting students' development of autonomous learning skills (Xu et al., 2023; Guo, 2022; Feraco et al., 2022). Teachers often face substantial challenges when implementing Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) in the classroom. These include limited instructional time, the need to accommodate diverse student learning styles, and a lack of targeted professional development. To cope, teachers adopt adaptive and flexible instructional strategies, often relying on collaborative support from colleagues, personal resilience, and student-centered approaches. Despite these efforts, the implementation remains inconsistent. Recent studies (Xu et al., 2023; Feraco et al., 2022; Guo, 2022) have emphasized the role of learning adaptability in shaping students' self-regulated learning (SRL) behaviors, highlighting its potential to improve engagement and learning outcomes. These challenges underscore the need for providing teach-

ers with ongoing, systematic training to help them develop confidence in adopting SRL methods. Strengthening both teacher and student adaptation can significantly enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of SRL implementation in diverse school settings.

3.2.2. Disengagement and Limited Students' Participation—Disengagement and limited student involvement pose substantial obstacles to the effective implementation of self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies, especially when learners resist taking the initiative or accepting responsibility for their academic progress (Xu, Zhang, Maeda, 2023). In response to this difficulty, teachers have implemented deliberate strategies that promote increased student engagement and autonomy. One strategy was to direct students to establish individualized learning objectives, such as recognizing story components or crafting a character analysis, which enhanced their awareness of progress and opportunities for improvement (Feraco et al., 2022). Enhancing activities and parent-teacher conferences were implemented to assist disengaged learners in cultivating a more supportive environment and bolstering motivation. Moreover, peer learning was utilized to foster collaborative engagement, enabling skilled students to support their classmates who needed additional attention and assistance (Shu-rong Cui-hong, 2023). These pragmatic treatments underscore the importance of adaptive instruction in re-engaging students and developing essential self-regulated learning competencies, including goal-setting, self-monitoring, and reflective thinking. Participant 10 shared a strategy encouraging students to take initiative in their English learning by promoting SRL components, such as goal-setting and self-monitoring—e.g., setting learning objectives and reflecting on comprehension. This aligns with Lim and Yeo (2021), who emphasized that fostering student agency through structured goal-setting enhances motivation and

engagement in low-participation contexts. Additionally, Xu, Zhang, and Maeda (2023) found that explicit self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies improve cognitive engagement in blended classroom settings. Participant 7 emphasized the use of simplified materials and complementary activities (e.g., parent-teacher conferences). These findings are supported by Sizemore and Lewalter (2024), who reported that external supports, such as family engagement and scaffolded materials, significantly bolster motivation in disengaged students. Additionally, Chang and Lin (2023) noted that adjusting content complexity enhances self-regulated learning (SRL) readiness among students with lower self-direction. Participant 9 advocated for peer learning, pairing capable students with those needing support to model self-regulatory behaviors. This is supported by Shu-rong and Cui-hong (2023), who found that co-regulated learning among peers boosts SRL strategy use and self-efficacy, and Munshi et al. (2022), who observed that peer scaffolding enhances accountability and metacognitive regulation. As expressed in the In-depth interview and their responses, the teachers' point of view emphasized a teaching approach that engages students in analyzing short stories by encouraging them to set personal learning goals, such as identifying story elements or practicing character analysis. The focus was on developing awareness of their comprehension, identifying areas for improvement, and actively enhancing their skills. Quick assessment methods, parent-teacher conferences, and enhancement activities were also utilized to support learning. Additionally, peer learning was employed as an effective strategy, pairing more proficient students with those needing additional support to foster collaborative improvement. Teachers implementing self-regulated learning (SRL) strate-

gies often face challenges such as promoting active student participation, managing instructional time effectively, and ensuring equitable access to learning resources. Many educators turn to collaborative support systems, targeted professional development, and student-centered interventions to address these issues. SRL involves students taking an active role in their learning by setting personal goals and striving toward academic success through self-directed efforts. It encompasses four key components: affective, cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational strategies (Lim Yeo, 2021). Figure 4 shows the dual challenges teachers have when applying Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) strategies, as well as their coping mechanisms. The figure's central theme is that, while teachers recognize the importance of SRL in encouraging student autonomy, responsibility, and academic success, its implementation in real-world classroom situations remains challenging and demanding. The illustration shows two important themes: disengagement and limited student participation, as well as teachers' adaptation and flexibility. These challenges often stem from students' lack of motivation, unfamiliarity with SRL strategies, and varying levels of self-discipline. Teachers report that even when they introduce SRL techniques, students sometimes struggle to apply them consistently without external reinforcement. Despite these setbacks, educators demonstrate resilience by modifying lesson structures, integrating goal-setting activities, and using formative assessments to monitor progress. The figure emphasizes how teachers' adaptability and persistence are key to addressing disengagement and fostering student autonomy. Ultimately, the illustration conveys that while SRL implementation is complex, it is achievable through continuous reflection, support, and innovation in instructional practice.

Fig. 4. Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Implementing Self- Regulated Learning Strategies and Their Coping Mechanisms

Teachers observed that many students lacked the motivation, initiative, or discipline to engage actively in SRL activities such as setting goals, self-monitoring, and reflecting on learning. This disengagement poses a significant barrier to SRL, which fundamentally depends on the learner’s active involvement and intrinsic motivation (Zimmerman, 2022). Without such engagement, the self-regulated learning cycle cannot be sustained, making fostering independent and strategic learners difficult. Teachers developed coping mechanisms that reflect adaptability and flexibility in their instructional approaches to address these challenges. Rather than rigidly adhering to traditional methods, educators adjusted their lesson pacing, differentiated instruction, and integrated supportive tools and strategies, including digital resources and scaffolding techniques. This flexible approach allowed teachers to respond to the diverse needs of their learners, helping them gradually take ownership of their learning process. According to Vosniadou et al. (2020), teachers’ instructional beliefs and adaptability significantly influence the success of SRL implementation in the

classroom. Similarly, Lim and Yeo (2021) emphasize the importance of collaborative support and teacher training in managing SRL-related challenges. Overall, the figure underscores that while the path to successful SRL integration is complex, teachers’ willingness to adapt and innovate plays a crucial role in navigating institutional barriers and promoting effective learning outcomes.

3.3. *Insights on the Effectiveness of Self-Regulated Learning Strategies for Promoting Academic Success* —Self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies are crucial in enhancing academic achievement, particularly in online learning contexts. SRL entails students proactively controlling their cognitive activities, motivation, and learning surroundings to deepen their comprehension and reach their educational objectives. By assuming responsibility for their learning process, students cultivate essential skills such as goal-setting, effective time management, self-monitoring, and adaptability, significantly boosting their academic success.

3.3.1. *High Teachers’ Motivation* —Teachers with high motivation play an important role

in encouraging self-regulated learning (SRL) practices that boost student confidence and academic growth. Their passion for empowering students is clear in how they encourage them to take control of their learning experience. Several teachers remarked that motivation increases when students build self-confidence, which SRL tactics naturally promote (Schunk DiBenedetto, 2020; Zhang, 2024). Teachers noticed significant gains in students' engagement and performance after assisting them in setting personal goals, managing time properly, and reflecting on their progress. Techniques such as using checklists after projects, encouraging self-assessment, and emphasizing strengths and areas for growth help students improve their skills while reinforcing their confidence in their talents. These efforts indicate how motivated teachers can help shape self-sufficient, confident students through consistent and purposeful SRL practices. Participant 2 (P2) highlighted the connection between students' confidence and motivation. According to this teacher, learners who feel competent and confident participate more actively in class and show greater persistence in completing tasks (Mega et al., 2021). By integrating SRL strategies into classroom routines, such as setting manageable goals or reflecting on progress, students begin to experience small wins that build their self-esteem (Karlen et al., 2020). Over time, these experiences help foster a stronger internal drive to learn, highlighting how a motivated teacher can plant the seeds of long-term academic confidence in their students (Hirt et al., 2022). Participant 4 (P4) shared practical observations of how SRL has directly influenced students' motivation and independence. According to this teacher, students who learn to manage their time and set specific goals often show increased enthusiasm for completing academic tasks (Sáiz-Manzanares et al., 2022). Instead of relying heavily on teacher instructions, learners gradually take control of their schedules and assignments. This shift reflects improved time management and the teacher's commitment to fostering student autonomy, demonstrating the motivational impact of structured and supportive Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) instruction (Dignath Veenman, 2021). Participant 8 (P8) discussed how encouraging students to monitor their academic journey enhances their ability to solve problems and build confidence. Using reflective tools, such as checklists, after a science project helped students better understand the content and the learning process (Lemos et al., 2022). This practice allowed them to recognize areas where they succeeded and parts where they could improve. By consistently guiding students through these self-evaluation routines, the teacher strengthened learners' trust in their problem-solving abilities—a key marker of self-regulation and intrinsic motivation (Hirt et al., 2022). Participant 10 (P10) noted that SRL strategies enable students to assess their capabilities more realistically. This awareness allows them to identify where to focus their efforts, resulting in more meaningful and efficient learning experiences (Sáiz-Manzanares et al., 2022). When students recognize their strengths and weaknesses, they are more likely to invest in their growth. The teacher's role, fueled by a strong sense of purpose and motivation, is to create conditions where learners feel safe and equipped to take those steps independently (Hirt et al., 2022). Teachers who perceive self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies as effective are more motivated to encourage their use in the classroom, which can lead to improved student outcomes. This heightened motivation is driven by their confidence in SRL's potential to boost student motivation, self-efficacy, and academic success. Additionally, teachers' beliefs in their capacity to implement SRL strategies (self-efficacy) and their genuine interest in promoting SRL significantly shape their motivation. Hirt et al. (2022) and Karlen et al. (2020) have highlighted the importance of motivation for teaching. However, relatively little research

has been conducted on teachers' motivation to promote Self-Regulated Learning (SRL). Thus, applying expectancy-value theory as a framework in the study of SRL can provide a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the different aspects of teachers' motivation and how these components may interact (Hirt et al., 2022).

3.3.2. Intensified Institutional Support — Institutional support is essential for effectively implementing schools' self-regulated learning (SRL) initiatives. Participants emphasized that offering enough tools, such as digital gadgets, meets the needs of today's learners, who rely heavily on technology (Lemos, Alves, Ferreira, 2022). However, institutional constraints such as restrictive curricula and tight schedules can create considerable barriers to incorporating SRL techniques into daily teaching, limiting teachers' ability to help students acquire these critical skills (Karlen, Hertel, Hirt, 2021). To overcome these problems, continual professional development and easily available instructional technologies can help teachers better assist student learning (Dignath Veenman, 2021). Furthermore, targeted advice and scaffolded support, particularly for students who struggle with self-regulation, can help them gradually improve their ability to regulate their learning. Such increased institutional efforts create a more conducive climate for developing student autonomy and reflection, critical self-regulated learning components. Participant2 (P2) highlighted the growing necessity for schools to equip students with digital gadgets and learning resources, acknowledging that modern learners were digital natives. This recognition highlighted the evolving nature of learning environments where technology integration was essential (Wu et al., 2023). Without such resources, students struggled to engage with learning tasks requiring digital literacy and full access. Therefore, providing these tools was fundamental to supporting SRL, as technology facilitated per-

sonalized learning, immediate feedback, and opportunities for students to manage their progress more effectively (Chen Lee, 2024). Participant3 (P3) highlighted significant institutional and administrative constraints, such as strict curriculum requirements and limited instructional time due to tight deadlines. These pressures restricted teachers' ability to teach and reinforce SRL strategies explicitly (Del Mario Tran, 2024). The overwhelming focus on content coverage and assessment compliance often sidelined the development of students' self-regulatory skills, which required dedicated time and reflective practice—underscoring the need for institutional flexibility or policy adjustments that prioritized SRL within the existing curriculum framework (Johnson Martin, 2022). Participant4 (P4) proposed a practical solution to these challenges by emphasizing professional development for teachers in SRL. By equipping educators with specialized training and providing tangible resources such as templates and instructional tools (Linde et al., 2023), schools empowered teachers to implement SRL more effectively. Such support enabled more structured and consistent integration of classroom self-regulation practices, helping students build autonomy and strategic learning habits systematically (Rodriguez Gomez et al., 2024). Participant5 (P5) focused on the importance of tailored support for students who faced difficulties with self-regulation. Recognizing that some learners required more guided assistance, P5 suggested that scaffolding—gradually reducing support as competence grew—helped these students develop their SRL skills (Munshi et al., 2022). Techniques like open-ended questioning and breaking complex tasks into manageable steps fostered deeper reflection and encouraged students to take incremental control of their learning (Lim et al., 2023). Participant6 (P6) echoed the concerns about institutional barriers, particularly the constraints of strict curricula and busy schedules that limited opportunities to teach

essential SRL practices like goal-setting and self-reflection (Del Mario Tran, 2024). This reiterated the systemic nature of the challenge, suggesting that without institutional changes to create space for these activities, students missed out on crucial skill development. Institutional policies and scheduling, therefore, needed to evolve to accommodate the integration of SRL strategies as an essential part of learning (Sui, Yen, Chang, 2023). The narratives of the interview participants in the in-depth interview discussions conveyed their perspectives. The school recognizes students as digital natives in the 21st century and aims to provide appropriate digital gadgets and resources to support their learning (Sui, Yen, Chang, 2023). However, institutional and administrative challenges, such as strict curricula and tight deadlines, hinder the implementation of self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies, as the focus on covering numerous topics and meeting assessment schedules leaves limited time for fostering these skills (DelMario Tran, 2024). Supporting students with self-regulation difficulties requires consistent guidance, gradual scaffolding, open-ended questions, task segmentation, and individualized assistance to help them build confidence and develop their abilities (Munshi et al., 2022). Addressing these challenges involves balancing curriculum demands with dedicated efforts to develop students' self-regulation (SRL) skills, including goal setting and self-reflection, despite the constraints posed by the school's tight schedules (Lemos, Alves, Ferreira, 2022).

3.3.3. Strengthened Parent and Teacher Collaboration—Effective communication between parents and teachers fosters self-regulated learning (SRL) among students. When parents are actively engaged and well-informed about SRL strategies—such as goal-setting, self-monitoring, and reflection—they are better equipped to support their children's learning at home (Wu, Zuo, Xu, 2023). This partnership helps create a consistent and sup-

portive environment where students can apply and reinforce SRL skills beyond the classroom. Teachers recognize that involving parents through regular communication, participation in school activities, and shared responsibility strengthens student motivation and ownership of their learning (Villareal, 2023). Ultimately, this collaborative approach enhances academic outcomes and builds learners' confidence, independence, and accountability. Participant1 emphasized the importance of regular communication with parents regarding self-regulation strategies. This response highlights a key insight: when parents are informed and engaged in how students are being trained to manage their learning—a point emphasized by Villareal (2023) and supported by Salac and Florida (2022)—it strengthens students' motivation and sense of independence. The teacher's observation suggests that even simple updates or conversations about SRL practices can empower learners by reinforcing these strategies at home. Participant4 shared a more in-depth experience, pointing out that when parents are involved in SRL practices like goal-setting and self-monitoring, students benefit from a more supportive learning environment beyond the classroom. Kim (2022) and Schmid and Garrels (2021) highlight that this involvement builds students' confidence, particularly when parents model reflective and organized learning behaviors. It also boosts academic performance, as students receive consistent reinforcement and feedback from their teachers and families. Participant3 framed parents as a bridge between school and home, helping students apply classroom-based SRL techniques daily. The response also lists practical ways parents can be engaged—through meetings, volunteering, and cooperative planning—which aligns with the findings of Sibanda (2021), who emphasizes that parent involvement is not limited to communication but also extends to active participation. This kind of engagement creates continuity in

learning and helps solidify SRL habits outside the school setting. Participant10 reflected on the broader impact of teacher-parent collaboration, noting its role in improving students' motivation and sense of responsibility. As Liu et al. (2020) and Villareal (2023) assert, when students observe that their learning is a shared priority between school and home, they tend to take more ownership of their actions and efforts. This also fosters a culture of accountability and encourages learners to monitor their progress more deliberately. Promoting self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies is crucial to academic achievement. Parenting styles that are authoritative and support autonomy, along with positive interactions between teachers and students, strengthen students' capacity to manage their learning (Salac Florida, 2022). Active parental involvement can also lead to more consistent homework completion, a deeper understanding of subjects, and improved academic performance. Salac Florida (2022) define parental involvement as the dynamic interaction between parents and their children, both at home and within the educational setting, significantly contributing to students' academic success. This concept encompasses four key dimensions: parents' aspirations and expectations for their children's academic achievements; participation in school-related activities and programs; creating a home environment conducive to learning; and ongoing dialogue with children regarding their educational experiences, as Sibanda (2021) added. The participants' responses highlighted the diverse strategies that teachers employed. Regular communication with parents about self-regulation strategies reinforces students' independence and motivation. Involving parents in SRL techniques like goal-setting and self-monitoring helps create a supportive home environment where modeling these behaviors and providing feedback boosts students' confidence and academic performance. Teachers view parents as essential partners in transferring classroom strategies to independent learning outside of school through attending meetings, volunteering, participating in events, and collaborating on student progress and behavior strategies. Collaboration between teachers and parents enhances students' motivation and sense of responsibility, contributing positively to their learning experience. This was supported by Liu et al. (2020), who confirmed that parents positively influence their children's academic outcomes by setting achievable expectations (Liu et al., 2020). Furthermore, Schmid and Garrels (2021) analyzed data obtained from 25 semi-structured interviews on the role of parental involvement in students' academic performance. Similarly, Kim (2022) examined 23 published studies investigating the relationship between parental involvement and student performance. Figure 5 illustrates that the success of self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies in enhancing academic achievement is significantly influenced by three main factors: high teacher motivation, intensified institutional support, and parent-teacher involvement. Motivated teachers are essential to inspire students, model effective self-regulated learning (SRL) techniques, and create a classroom environment conducive to autonomous learning. Moreover, intensified institutional support provides the necessary resources, policies, and programs that encourage the adoption of SRL strategies, ensuring that these practices are integrated into the school culture. Parent-teacher involvement reinforces students' learning outside the classroom by offering guidance, encouragement, and opportunities, and creating a consistent support system from the school. The synergy of motivated teachers, supportive institutions, and active parental engagement creates an ecosystem that fosters students' self-regulation skills, leading to increased motivation, enhanced engagement, and improved academic success. Likewise, collaborative efforts among educators, administrators, and families are important in maximizing the benefits of SRL

Fig. 5. Insights on the Effectiveness of Self-Regulated Learning Strategies for Promoting Academic Success strategies.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter summarizes the study’s findings. It outlines the implications and suggests potential directions for future research. The research focused on the personal experiences of junior high school teachers in District 2, Cluster 14, Division of Davao City, regarding applying self-regulated learning strategies in their teaching practices. The design of this study is qualitative, utilizing a narrative inquiry approach to explore these experiences. Narrative inquiry is particularly well-suited for this study, as it enables an in-depth exploration of how teachers understand and interpret their experiences with self-regulated learning strategies, focusing on the meaning they attach to these strategies and their impact on academic success. It also examined the challenges teachers encounter when implementing these strategies and the coping mechanisms or strategies they employ to overcome these obstacles. Additionally, the study provides insights into teachers’ perceptions of the impact and effectiveness of self-regulated learning strategies in improving students’ academic success. It explores teachers’ lived experiences and aims to highlight how their unique perspectives contribute to a broader understanding of applying self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms. It seeks to illuminate teachers’ coping strategies in response to the demands of integrating technology with traditional instruction and their insights into best practices for effectively teaching scientific concepts in a blended context.

4.1. Implications—The study’s findings were derived from the participants’ viewpoints and highlighted several significant outcomes. The junior high school teachers’ diverse experiences offer a compelling glimpse into their personal experiences with implementing self-regulated learning strategies in their classrooms. The data highlights a mixed bag of outcomes, with some teachers successfully fostering innovation and teaching students to manage their time efficiently. Likewise, it revealed significant challenges, particularly the persistent issue

of student disengagement and limited participation, which teachers report as a significant barrier to the practical application of these strategies. However, the ability of students to independently problem-solve, a key component of self-regulated learning, is another area where teachers encounter difficulties, suggesting that while the intention to promote these skills is present, the practical application and student uptake are not consistently successful. The challenges and coping mechanisms involved in implementing self-regulated learning strategies are significant, as teachers often encounter obstacles when applying self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies. These challenges include difficulties adapting and being flexible in their teaching methods, ensuring active student participation, and facilitating meaningful discussions. Teachers employ various coping mechanisms to overcome these obstacles, including adopting adaptable lesson plans, creating inclusive and engaging activities, and developing facilitation skills to guide practical discussions. These strategies help foster a supportive environment that promotes student autonomy and enhances the overall effectiveness of SRL implementation. The insights regarding the impact and effectiveness of self-regulated learning strategies in enhancing academic success among students, such as the success of self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies in enhancing academic achievement, are significantly influenced by three main factors: high teacher motivation, intensified institutional support, and strengthened parent and teacher collaboration. Motivated teachers are essential to inspire students, model effective self-regulated learning (SRL) techniques, and create a classroom environment conducive to autonomous learning. Moreover, intensified institutional support provides the necessary resources, policies, and programs that encourage the adoption of SRL strategies, ensuring that these practices are integrated into the school culture. Parent-teacher collaboration reinforces students' learning outside the classroom by offering guidance, encouragement, and opportunities, and creating a consistent support system from the school. The synergy of motivated teachers, supportive institutions, and active parental engagement creates an ecosystem that fosters students' self-regulation skills, leading to increased motivation, enhanced engagement, and improved academic success. Likewise, collaborative efforts among educators, administrators, and families are important in maximizing the benefits of SRL strategies. Self-regulated learning (SRL) has significant implications for both teaching and learning. When teachers incorporate Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) strategies, they empower students to take ownership of their learning, leading to improved academic performance, enhanced motivation, and better time management. SRL also encourages critical thinking, problem-solving, and lifelong learning skills. Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) strategies enhance students' academic performance by fostering proactive and practical learning, leading to higher grades and a deeper understanding of the material. They also boost motivation and engagement as students feel more in control of their learning. Additionally, SRL promotes better time management through planning and progress monitoring. SRL cultivates lifelong learning skills and enhances critical thinking and problem-solving abilities by empowering students to become independent learners. Teachers play a crucial role as facilitators, guiding students in developing these essential self-regulation skills. This finding is supported by the results of previous studies, which have mainly demonstrated the positive effects of self-regulatory learning based on this theory. This study is anchored in Zimmerman's Self-Regulated Learning Theory and Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory. However, it is worth noting that some studies have reported a positive impact on student engagement when using self-regulatory learning approaches, such as

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, to explore self-regulated learning strategies. The implications of this study extend beyond teachers' individual experiences to influence educational policy, curriculum development, and teacher training programs. By understanding how educators adapt and innovate within self-regulatory learning environments, stakeholders can implement strategies that enhance the teaching and learning process, ultimately benefiting students' grasp of scientific concepts.

4.1.1. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, it was important that the key people for whom this research was meant convey and apply them effectively.

4.1.2. The Teachers—Teachers who recognize the diverse differences within their classrooms tend to be better informed and more aware of their student's unique needs. By acknowledging these differences, teachers can tailor their lessons and discussions to fit their students' contexts better, promoting increased engagement and participation, especially in science classes. Self-regulated learning (SRL) is vital in helping students reach high academic achievement and accomplish their learning goals online. Nonetheless, many learners struggle to apply SRL strategies in virtual learning environments effectively.

4.1.3. The School Principals/School Heads—They may be more proactive and supportive in promoting effective teachers and self-regulatory learning activities, especially in schools with students from remote areas that lack internet access. Classroom management can make or break a teacher; it can be the difference between a focus on learning and a focus on struggling for control. There were bad days, but there was also potential for glorious ones—struggling teachers must partner with those who have honed successful strategies. Administrators must be quick to encourage teachers and support them with definitive action.

4.1.4. Other Stakeholders/Parents—As key stakeholders in the education process, parents play a crucial role in supporting teachers and students to enhance the overall learning experience. Their active involvement is essential for effectively implementing Self-Regulated Learning (SRL), which is closely linked to student engagement. SRL encourages learners to control their learning by setting goals, monitoring progress, and adapting strategies as needed. This fosters a strong sense of responsibility and ownership, resulting in increased motivation, sustained effort, and improved academic performance. By collaborating with teachers and modelling self-regulation practices at home, parents help reinforce these vital skills, ensuring that students remain actively engaged in their learning inside and outside the classroom.

4.1.5. The Department of Education—The findings of this study may be beneficial to the Department of Education, as they offer valuable insights into teachers' experiences in a classroom setting. They may also assess how far the Department of Education has progressed and formulate ways and programs to enhance and improve it. They could also support and assist teachers with teaching materials for their lessons. Self-regulated learning is important because it enhances student engagement by fostering proactive and practical learning, leading to higher grades and a deeper understanding of the material. They also boost motivation and engagement as students feel more in control of their learning. Additionally, SRL promotes better time management through planning and progress monitoring. SRL cultivates lifelong learning skills and enhances critical thinking and problem-solving abilities by empowering students to become independent learners. Teachers play a crucial role as facilitators, guiding students in developing these essential self-regulation skills.

4.1.6. Future Researchers—Future researchers may conduct similar studies, tak-

ing the students' perspective on self-regulation diverse classmates. They may also explore dif-
 learning and focusing on their experiences and ferent challenges and strategies to open new
 the challenges they face in a diverse class with avenues to improve learners' learning.

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